

MMCS FABRICATED BY REACTION SQUEEZE CASTING AND ITS APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

Reaction squeeze casting is a newly developed process to fabricate the intermetallics-distributed MMCs, in which the process is effectively taken advantage of the reaction between a certain reinforcement and molten metal. The process offers the heat- and wear-resistive MMCs with a low cost. The paper deals with the effect of process parameter on the hardness of TiO₂/Al composites, such as temperature of molten aluminum and preform, TiO₂ powder diameter, volume fraction and heat treatment of the composites. The in-process reaction and the off-process reaction are successful to control the microstructure and hardness of the composites up to 750Hv. The process has been applied to produce the diesel engine piston and the cylinder liner for gasoline engine.

INTRODUCTION

The aluminum matrix composites are requested to resist at higher temperature service, while the engineering plastic matrix composites are catching up the conventional aluminum matrix composites. The reaction squeeze casting process[1] has been newly developed to improve the high-temperature properties of the MMCs by promoting positively the reaction between a certain reinforcement and molten aluminum, resulting to the intermetallics-distributed aluminum matrix. There are two cases of the reaction: in-process reaction during squeeze casting and off-process reaction after squeeze casting. The outline of the in-process is illustrated in Fig.1. The oxide powder, such as TiO₂ and NiO, and the metal powder such as Ni, Fe and Cu are embedded in the fiber preform. The conventional squeeze casting process is applied on the preform, then the reaction is taken place at the melt front, for example as following equations, resulting to produce intermetallic compounds.

The reaction products of Al₂O₃, TiAl₃ and NiAl₃ are effective for improving the matrix strength at elevated temperatures and the wear resistance of MMC. The MMC displayed higher strength at

Fig.1. Process of Reaction Squeeze Casting

elevated temperatures comparing to a conventional one. The composites which are fabricated by reaction squeeze casting employing the preform of 20%SiCw+5%TiO₂+5%Ni and molten pure aluminum, keep the bending strength of 320MPa still at 400°C while the conventional one bears just 90MPa at the same temperature[2]. The X-ray diffraction technique identified Al₂O₃, TiAl₃, Ti₃Al and NiAl₃ in the new composites.

The experimental report increases in number in which deals with the fabrication of MMC by utilizing the reaction between the solid reinforcement and the molten metal. Suganuma[3], Nishida[4] and Horsfall[5] carried out successfully the reaction squeeze casting by employing the couple of 5%Ni powder+Al₂O₃·SiO₂ short fiber/molten Al alloy, 50%Ti fiber/molten pure aluminum, and Ti powder+Al₂O₃ short fiber/molten aluminum, respectively.

As for the off-process, the isothermal heat treatment causes the reaction products in the composites and the strengthen the matrix, after fabricating the non-reacted composites by squeeze casting at considerably lower temperature conditions[6,7]. The process enables the matrix hardness from Hv 200 to 750, and it is easy to control the hardness because the reaction takes place very slowly.

In the paper, the effect of fabricating conditions, such as, volume fraction of TiO₂ powder, crystalline structure and diameter of the powder, and molten aluminum temperature, on the matrix hardness is investigated for the in-process reaction squeeze casting. Aiming the practical application of this process to the automobile engine parts, the Al₂O₃-short fiber as reinforcement and the TiO₂-anatase powder as the reactive additives were employed to produce the wear resisting and high strength composites at the temperature of 250 to 350°C. Some trial fabrications and the testing were carried out on the diesel engine piston and the cylinder liner for gasoline engine.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

TiO₂ powder was employed here, because it is reactive with molten aluminum and had been commercially produced. Properties of TiO₂ are shown in Table 1. As for the crystal structure of TiO₂, anatase type and rutile type were employed. The rutile type of TiO₂ is comparatively stable at a high temperature. The industrial pure aluminum is used for fundamental experiment as a matrix. Particles of TiO₂ with no binder are previously pressed to the preform in diameter of 24mm, of the height of 20mm by using a metal die before reaction squeeze casting, and occasionally with the certain volume fraction of Al₂O₃ fiber in case of low volume fraction of powder. The conventional squeeze casting operation was applied on the preform in the conditions

Table.1 Properties of TiO2

Crystal structure	Density (g/cm ³)	Shape	Length (μm)	Mean diameter (μm)
Anatase	3.9	Whisker	13	0.5
		Particle	—	0.4
			—	12
Rutile	4.2	Particle	—	0.4
			—	1.8
			—	11.8

Table.2 Experimental Parameter

Parameter	Conditions
T _m : Temperature of Molten Al	740~830 (°C)
T _p : Temperature of Preform	380~500 (°C)
d : Diameter of TiO ₂ Particle	0.4~12 (μm)
V _f : Volume Fraction of TiO ₂	0~56 (%)
Crystal Structure	Anatase / Rutile
Shape of TiO ₂	Particle / Whisker

of Table 2. In this experiment, a speed of plunger is fixed to 10mm/s, and the final squeeze pressure to 50MPa.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1) Effects of temperature of molten Al and preform

In the case of employing anatase type of TiO₂, the effect of fabricating temperature on the hardness of composites is shown in Fig.2 and Fig.3. As the temperature of preform or molten Al is raised, the hardness is increased, too. In the case of rutile type of TiO₂, the results are shown in Fig.4 and Fig.5. In these figures, the diameter of TiO₂ is varied as a parameter. For the rutile type of TiO₂, there is little effect of fabricating temperature on the hardness, regardless of diameter. The reason is that rutile type of TiO₂ is more stable than anatase type at high temperature[6].

Fig.2 Effect of temperature of molten Al on hardness

Fig.3 Effect of temperature of preform on hardness

V_f : volume fraction of TiO₂
T_p : temperature of preform

T_m : temperature of molten aluminum
d : diameter of TiO₂ particle

Fig.4 Effect of temperature of molten Al on hardness

Fig.5 Effect of temperature of preform on hardness

2) Effect of diameter

Effect of mean diameter of TiO₂ (rutile) on the hardness of the composites was shown roughly in Fig.5. With the decrease in the diameter of the powder, the hardness of the composites is increased. Especially, when the diameter of 0.4 μm powder is employed, the hardness is raised remarkably to 800Hv. Analysis of X-ray diffraction pattern of the composites with 0.4 μm and 11.8 μm of TiO₂ showed as follows: the specimen with d=0.4 μm includes Al₂O₃ (Hv=1600~2700), TiAl₃ (Hv=400~700) and Ti₃Al. These reaction products cause the high hardness of composites. On the other hand, the specimen with d=11.8 μm had scarcely the reaction products, and the reaction has not finished yet. The hardness of specimen(d=11.8 μm) was low and about 130 Hv.

Figure 6 shows SEM photograph of the composites in case of 0.4 μm powder and in case of 11.8 μm powder. As shown in Fig.6, many of unreacted 11.8 μm powders exist in the specimen. On the other hand, for 0.4 μm powder, some phases which are different from the initial powder shape is observed in the photograph. The phases were identified to be intermetallic compounds by EPMA. The temperature of the preform was measured by embedding the thermocouple in it during squeeze casting. For 0.4 μm powder, the peak temperature of the preform was raised up to 1300 °C. This temperature is considerably high, and has lasted for about 0.5sec. So high temperature is generated and the reaction compounds are created quickly. After all, whole amounts of the TiO₂ has reacted with molten aluminum spontaneously. In case of a preform made from 11.8 μm powder, the temperature was measured up to 640 °C. The temperature corresponded to the balanced temperature of mixtures from heat exchange. However X-ray diffraction showed that specimen did has TiAl₃ phase as the reaction products. It means that the reaction takes place a little, and the temperature rise by reaction may be small, so the reaction does not proceed moreover. After all, TiO₂ of the large diameter and of the rutile type is left unreacted.

Fig.6 SEM photograph of reaction squeeze casting products

3) Effect of volume fraction

Figure.7 shows the effect of volume fraction on the hardness. The experiment is carried out on the anatase type of TiO₂ powder and whisker. From the figure, as a volume fraction is increased, the hardness is increased, too. Especially, when the volume fraction is increased from 25% to 30%, the hardness is raised from 200 Hv to 750 Hv suddenly. The possible reason comes from as follows: when the volume fraction is large, the molten Al/TiO₂ contact area is large, and the fraction of aluminum is small. So the heat generated by reaction per unit volume increases and the reaction temperature is raised to overcome the heat divergence to matrix. Finally, when a volume fraction is raised from 25% to 30%, the reaction proceeds rapidly by one powder to another powder.

Fig.7 Effect of volume fraction on hardness.

4) Effect of isothermal heat treatment

There is almost no reaction in the rutile type TiO₂/Al composites fabricated at comparatively low temperature conditions, less than 700 °C for molten aluminum temperature and 300°C for preform temperature. The composites are possibly hardened by the isothermal heat treatment after squeeze casting. Figure 8 shows the microstructures of the composites before and after heat treatment at 700 °C for 10 minutes. TiO₂ particles are covered with the white reaction layer, it is observed by EDX that Ti contents become rich in the matrix. Figure 9 shows the hardness change of the composites with increase in heat treatment time at various isothermal temperatures. The reaction proceeds slowly in the composites, then the hardness increases gradually, and saturates to about 750 Hv in 10⁶ seconds at each temperature. The curves tell us the hardness of the composites is now controllable.

Fig.8 Microstructure of composites before and after heat treatment

Fig.9 Hardening curve of TiO₂/Al composites by heat treatment.

FABRICATION OF OBJECTIVE PARTS FOR APPLICATION

The TiO₂/Al alloy composites with small volume fraction of Al₂O₃ short fiber fabricated by reaction squeeze casting has several superior features: 1) Case hardening and partial strengthening of Al alloy parts, 2) As good wear resistivity as cast iron and lighter weight, 3) Higher service temperature than conventional MMC, 4) Comparatively low cost.

The diesel engine piston and the cylinder liner for gasoline engine is a good target to apply the MMC fabricated by reaction squeeze casting. The components (Fig. 10 and 11) were planned to fabricate practically in the factory and the built-in engine testing have been carried out. Through the program, the instructive issues are shown as follows;

The uniform distribution of TiO₂ powder in the preform is highly required. To establish that, the

Fig.10 10%TiO₂ whisker+10%Al₂O₃ short fiber /AC8A piston ($\phi 85 \times 55$) fabricated by reaction squeeze casting and wear-tested on ring groove. (350ton vertical squeeze machine, T_m=800°C, T_p=600°C T_d=250-300°C, p=50MPa, HB=151, T6)

Fig.11 12%TiO₂ powder+15%Al₂O₃ short fiber/AC4C cylinder liner ($\phi 95 \times 120$, bottom) fabricated by reaction squeeze casting and cylinder block(top) with the liners.

wet process, i.e.the slurry of powder/fiber and water, then filtering in the plastic mold with many small holes at the bottom , is the best among the method experienced here. The condensation of powder decreases the reactivity and apt to make sintered ceramic spots. Figure 12 show microstructure of preform and composites illustrating the comparison of powder and whisker in the preform. From the optical microscope of the composites, the whisker type is well distributed in the composites. However there is no difference of the Vickers hardness between whisker and powder type. Table 3 shows the top ring groove wear at the temperature of 250°C subjecting to the normal pulsating load of 6MPa with 20Hz for 3 hours under hot lubricant condition as a counter material of steel piston ring. The 10%TiO₂+10%Al₂O₃/AC8A composites fabricated by reaction squeeze casting is durable for piston and excellent wear resistivity. The composites also characterized by less adhesivity to the piston ring. As for the casting process concerned, it is important to prevent the preform from cracking by designing the proper die to minimize the tensile stress exerting on the preform.

Table 3 Wear test result on top ring groove of piston

Piston materials	Wear (mg)
Aluminum alloy	4020
Niresist cast iron	460
12%Al ₂ O ₃ short fiber/AC8A,T6	77
5%TiO ₂ whisker+10%Al ₂ O ₃ short fiber/AC8A,T6	30
10%TiO ₂ whisker+10%Al ₂ O ₃ short fiber/AC8A,T6	31
5%TiO ₂ powder+10%Al ₂ O ₃ short fiber/AC8A,T6	51
10%TiO ₂ powder+10%Al ₂ O ₃ short fiber/AC8A,T6	45

5%TiO₂ powder+10%Al₂O₃ short fiber 5%TiO₂ whisker+10%Al₂O₃ short fiber

Fig.12 SEM photograph of preform(top) fabricated by slurry method and optical microphotograph of the composites(bottom) with hardness HB=122-124.

The cylinder liner of 12%TiO₂+15%Al₂O₃/AC4C composites has 60% weight cut comparing to the conventional liner of cast iron. The built-in motoring test at 1600 rpm for 1000 hrs did not have the detectable wear while the conventional MMC cylinder had 0.1mg wear. The composites has coefficient of thermal expansion of 20×10^{-7} . There was a difficulty, when the cylinder block were cast together with MMC cylinder liners in the conventional casting production line: it accompanied the corner cracking and adhesion at inner surface with MMC liners. Some modification of process conditions has to be done and will shoot the troubles in case of a large scale production.

The trial fabrication and checking test proved that the composites fabricated by reaction squeeze casting is applicable for various engine component oriented to the light weight and the high performance.

SUMMARY

- 1) The anatase type of TiO₂ was more reactive than the rutile type of TiO₂, and easy to produce hard MMCs at the same fabricating conditions.
- 2) In most cases of both anatase type and rutile type, as the particle size is increased in diameter, the hardness of composites decreases. The hardness of composites achieves to Hv 150 to 800 depending on fabricating conditions.
- 3) As for the effect of the diameter and volume fraction on the hardness, there is the transition volume fraction and diameter of TiO₂, respectively.
- 4) The as-cast TiO₂/Al composites with little reaction is controlled the hardness between 200 Hv and 750 Hv by isothermal heat treatment.
- 5) TiO₂+Al₂O₃/Al alloy composites offers the case hardening and the partial strengthening for Aluminum parts, and superior wear resistivity to cast iron.

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